

Depression among the Unemployed Educated Person in India

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Abstract

Through the present study, the investigators have tried to study what kind of Depression of Unemployed Educated Person and to find out the unemployed Educated Person concerning their level of Depression on the basics Category. The investigators have used the Descriptive type Survey method for the present study. The Simple Random sampling technique has been used for the selection of the sample. The investigators used self-made questionnaires. For the analysis of data, Mean, S.D., 't' test, ANOVA, and graph have been used in the present study. The overall results of the study explored that the level of Depression of Unemployed Educated Person is being Moderate in India. It is revealed that the Female Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than the Males Unemployed Educated Person and Urban Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Rural Unemployed Educated Person. Through the present study, It was also found that there is significantly affected among the Unemployed Educated Person concerning their level of Depression on the basis of Educational Qualification. It is also investigated that there is no significant difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Age groups, but the level of depression increases with age. It was also there is the significant difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Educational Qualification and the Unemployed Educated Person who passed Higher Secondary School is comparatively low depressed than other Educational Qualification persons and the Unemployed Educated Person who passed B.A/B.Sc/B.Com is comparatively high depressed than other Educational Qualification persons. This study will be helpful for the parents, teachers, administrators, counselors, Guide, Scholar, psychologist as well as our society to treat the Unemployed Educated Person in a better way.

Contribution/Originality of the Study: Through the present study, it was found that Female Unemployed Educated Person and Unemployed Educated Person who passed B.A/B.Sc/B.Com is high depressed. It was a novel finding of the study.

Introduction

Every human being in this world has some goals or needs. Normally, every human being fails to achieve a goal or need some times. Depression is the state of mind that arises when there is an obstacle in the way of achieving a goal. That is to say when the fulfillment of the demand is hindered that is called Depression. It is a state of mind when a man depressed then self-confidence and self-esteem are severely damaged. When obstacles and repugnance rapidly increase in a person, the proportion of Depression increases in the same way. Depression is one kind of knowing mental disorders across the world. It is exposed as Decay from before use with the existence of various psychological difficulties. Such as a depressed manner, a decrease of pleasure or interest, feelings of regret or uselessness, suicidal mood, along with some somatic symptoms that contain important weight change, sleep problems, problems of concentrating, and physical health, etc (Bakhtyari, 2018). Depression destroys a person's deep interest and increases stress. India is the second-largest populated country in the world where the population is growing day by day but the opportunity of a job has not increased much. So people have become unemployed. Depression is more common in older people who have not been able to find Jobs for a long time (Liwowsky et. al., 2009). Anxiety, Depression, Stress are an integral part of unemployed persons (Imam & Ansari, 2018). Especially the problem of unemployment among them is intensifying after educated people finish their studies. Although different governments give different promises at different times, there is a big difference between promises and opportunities for a job later. As a result, the problem of the educated unemployed person remains the same in a dark situation. Although there were vacancies in various sectors of the government, the government was not able to fill them due to a lack of economical funds. In our

country, many students are getting higher education every year but the amount of job opportunities is limited to very few students. In many cases, there are allegations of government corruption in recruitment. So the educated unemployed person is getting frustrated day by day.

Among them, the unemployed educated person showed the attitude of suicide as well as alcohol and substance abuse due to excessive frustration (Karakus, 2018). Mortality rates, depression, admissions to psychiatric hospitals, and violence are increase among unemployment persons (Rodriguez, 1999). Most of the families in India live below the poverty line. When persons are educated and do not get any job, extreme depression can be noticed among them. Because of this depression, they often become emotionally weak. The relationship between depression and social relations can only be explained from a performance perspective (Chen & Li 2000). Depression is the expression of an experience of unhappiness or suffering. Depression is a person's weakness, helplessness, worry, distraction, etc (Safree et al. 2011). Depression is a disorder that is affecting more and more people when arises a lack of interest in his workplace. It helps the person to increase various emotions and physical problems. It also helps reduce a person's ability at home and work (Wahab 2019). There is a long-standing relationship between mental health and social relationships. Disclosure of social relationships can be observed through the expression of various types of behavioral strategies such as health-related behavior, participation in social programs, and exchange various social supports (Teo et al. 2013). When depressed persons try to exaggerate their failures and weaknesses, they tend to neglect their successes and strengths (Khurshid et al. 2015). Unemployment increases a person's depression, stress, anxiety, decrease self-esteem, and worsens a person's physical health (Linn et al. 1985).

Need And Significance Of The Study

In order to organize the present society in a healthy and normal way, the present study can be useful for administrators, teachers, parents, planners, and members of the society who deal with a depressed person. Generally, every people want to job after complete their study. Next, they apply for proper jobs in various organizations e.g. government and private. But when they have not an opportunity to job in this organization then depression comes out in their mind, and they cannot adjust themselves with society. That's why Unemployed Educated Person are losing their self-worth and self-esteem through the daily comparison and competition that they experience. Through this study, we shall know the level of depression among Unemployed Educated Person. And also it will help the parents, teachers, Guide, scholars, administrators, counselors, psychologists as well as our society to treat the Unemployed Educated Person in a better way. The researchers think this study will help a researcher dealing with the topic, to a great extent.

Review Of Related Literature

Chen, Wenjun (2018) has conducted a study on "Academic Stress, Depression, and Social Support: A Comparison of Chinese Students in International Baccalaureate Programs and Key Schools" indicated that Female Key school students were more likely to report a higher level of depression compared to male students when they were experiencing a similar level of academic stress. Anitha and chowdary (2018) have investigated a Study of "Depression among Medical Students" revealed that depression is more among the female students when compared to male students and the difference is statistically significant ($p=0.02$). Pachaiyappan and Siranjeevi (2018) have conducted a study on "A Study on Depression and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students" revealed that The most of higher secondary students have a moderate level of depression and academic achievement and with regard to gender, the female higher secondary students have higher depression compared to male students but there is no significant difference in academic achievement with respect to gender. Karmakar, T, and Behera, S. K(2017) have conducted a study on "Depression among the College Students: An Empirical Study" revealed that there is significant difference exists between Rural and Urban College students in regard to depression and there is no significant difference exists between gender (Male & Female), religion (Hindu & Muslim) and Stream (Science & Arts), SC college students are more than another category (OBC, SC, and ST) with regard to depression. Makelele and Wewirhu (2017) through this study "Measure of the Depression at Psychology Students" explained that the gender difference in depression remains significant across most depression diagnostic studies whereas women are considered as more depressive than men and it is often confirmed that the women are more subject to the depression. Naik and Padikkal (2016) have examined on "Depression among College Students of Gulbarga City" revealed that there could not find significant difference on depression among male and female college students, but findings showed that there is a significant difference on depression among science and arts, and rural and urban. Kim and Knesebeck (2016) have conducted a study on "Perceived job insecurity, unemployment, and depressive symptoms: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective observational studies" explored that both perceived job insecurity and unemployment form a significant risk of increased depressive indication in prospective observational studies and comparing both stressors, job insecurity can pose a comparable risk of following depressive symptoms. Khurshid et al. (2015) have explained a study on "Effects of Depression on Students' Academic Performance through their study" result showed that there is a negative effect of depression

on student's academic performance whereas there is a significant difference between the academic performance of the students having low, medium and high-level depression. [Stirling et al. \(2015\)](#) have conducted a study on "Community factors influencing child and adolescent depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis" explored that community safety and community minority ethnicity and discrimination act which risk factors for depressive symptoms in school-aged children. The role of disadvantage may be influenced by other factors as well as Community connectedness was also not directly associated with depressive symptoms. [Kingsley and Christopher \(2014\)](#) have investigated the study on "Cognitive Distortions and Depression among Undergraduate Students" reported that a positive and significant relationship between cognitive distortions and depression and also found that no relationship was found between age and cognitive distortions and depression. [Ahmad and Mazlan \(2014\)](#) have conducted a study on "Stress and Depression: A Comparison Study between Men and Women Inmates in Peninsular Malaysia" Comparison analysis explored that stress and depression were significantly higher in female inmates than in male inmates. And also explored stress and depression showed significant association in both male and female inmates. [Dhara and Jogsan \(2013\)](#) have conducted a study on "Depression and Psychological Well-being in Old Age" revealed that a significant difference in depression and psychological well being with respect to both adult and aged. While co-relation between depression and psychological well-being reveals -0.70 negative correlation. [Basnet et al. \(2012\)](#) have investigated on "Depression Among Undergraduate Medical Students" reported that the prevalence of depression among medical students at different levels of education and find about their stressors. And the result showed that first and third-year students gave high ratings to academic stress and hectic lifestyle as the main stress-inducing factors. [Czoeshi and Inko-Tariah \(2011\)](#) in a study on "Sources of Depression among Unemployed University Graduates in Portharcourt Municipality of Rivers State, Nigeria" showed that that male university undergraduates experience more depression than their female counterparts and also showed that old university unemployed graduate encounter more depression than the young ones. [Yousefi et al. \(2010\)](#) have conducted a study on "The Relationship between Gender, Age, Depression, and Academic Achievement" The results reported that 27.5% of the boys and 31.5% of the girls were depressed and that depression and academic achievement were significantly correlated, $r = -0.22$, $p \leq 0.000$. Also, based on the results of the present study, age and academic achievement were significantly correlated ($r = 0.23$, $p \leq 0.000$). [Arslan et al. \(2009\)](#) through their study on "Prevalence of depression, its correlates among students, and its effect on health-related quality of life in a Turkish university" revealed that the prevalence of depression in university students was relatively high throughout our study, reaching almost one-fourth (21.8%). [Yeh et al. \(2007\)](#) through their study on "Correlations between Academic Achievement and Anxiety and Depression in Medical Students experiencing Integrated Curriculum Reform" revealed that the results of this study are both positive and negative correlations between academic achievement and anxiety and depression in medical students. And also different levels of sharpness of anxiety or depression. [Kapustinskiene et al. \(2006\)](#) have investigated a study on "Duration of unemployment and depression: a cross-sectional survey in Lithuania" explored that depression is more dominant among the long-term unemployed people. Being female, older age, and a growing number of unemployment episodes have a significant effect on the development of depression. [Afifi \(2006\)](#) through their study on "Depression in adolescents: gender differences in Oman and Egypt" explored that the rate of having depressive symptoms of girls was almost twice than of boys in Alexandria, Egypt and there was no significant difference in Depression on the basis of gender in Oman. [Heubeck et al. \(1995\)](#) through this study "Models of responsibility and Depression in Unemployed Young Male and Females" result showed that there was also no gender difference in causal attribution and no differential relationship with indicators of distress.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To assess the Depression of unemployed Educated Person in India.
2. To find out the difference between boys and girls unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
3. To find out the difference between Rural and Urban unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
4. To find out the difference between Rural Boys and Rural girls unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
5. To find out the difference between Urban Boys and Urban girls unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
6. To find out the difference between Rural Boys and Urban Boys unemployed Educated person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
7. To find out the difference between Rural Girls and Urban Girls unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
8. To find out the difference among unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Category. (UR, SC, ST and OBC).

9. To find out the difference among unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Age.
10. To find out the difference among the unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Qualification. (H.S, B.A/B.Sc/B.Com, M.A/M.Sc/M.Com, B.Ed/M.Ed & M.Phil/Ph.D)
11. To find out the difference among the unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of State.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- H0₁:** There would not have high favorable level of Depression of unemployed Educated Person in The India.
- H0₂:** There is no significant difference between Males and Females unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
- H0₃:** There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in The India.
- H0₄:** There is no significant difference between Rural Males and Rural Females unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
- H0₅:** There is no significant difference between Urban Males and Urban Females unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
- H0₆:** There is no significant difference between Rural Males and Urban Males unemployed Educated person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
- H0₇:** There is no significant difference between Rural Females and Urban Females unemployed Educated person in respect to their level of Depression in India.
- H0₈:** There is no significance difference among unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Category. (UR,SC,ST and OBC)
- H0₉:** There is no significance difference among unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Age.
- H0₁₀:** There is no significance difference among the unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Qualification. (H.S, B.A/B.Sc/B.Com, M.A/MSc/M.Com & M.phil/P.hD)
- H0₁₁:** There is no significance difference among the unemployed Educated Person in respect to their level of Depression on the basis of State.

The Methodology Of The Study

The nature of the present study is a descriptive type. The researcher has used the survey method of Descriptive type in the present study. The researcher has selected among 149 Unemployed Educated Person who were prepared for Job in the different states of India as a sample for the present study. The Simple Random sampling technique has been applied in the selection of the sample. The researcher has applied Depression Scale as a research tool for collecting the data in the present study. The researcher himself constructed a self-made Questionnaire which consists of 27 (twenty-seven) questions related to their Depression. The researcher himself constructed a Scale on the basis of five Important Dimensions, namely- (i) Sense of failure, (ii) Work inhibition, (iii) Lack of Satisfaction, (iv) Self-accusation, (v) Mood. The Inventory consisted of 27 Items (18 Items are Positive and 9 Items are Negative) which were distributed into the above five dimensions. The Inventory was constructed on the basis of Likert's Five Point Scale i.e. Always (A), Often (O), Sometimes (S), Rare (R), and Not at all (NA). The value of the coefficient of correlation of the present research tool was 0.83 which indicates that the tool was highly reliable. And in case of measuring the validity of the tools, the Expert Judgment Method was applied by the researcher in order to measure the validity of the tool (Singh, 2009). The present researcher has used SPSS (Version-20) followed by the techniques which are mentioned below to analyze the data: MEAN; S.D.; 't'-Test; ANOVA and Graph.

Results And Interpretation

H0₁: There would not have high favorable level of Depression of unemployed Educated Person in The India.

Analysis of Depression of unemployed Educated Person on the basis of cut off point

Table No-1: Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of Total Unemployed Educated Person

Group	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation
Person	149	81.94	15.76

$$M \pm \sigma$$

$$M + \sigma = 81.94 + 15.76 = 97.70$$

$$M - \sigma = 81.94 - 15.76 = 66.18$$

Table No-2, Show the level of Depression of the Unemployed Educated Person on basis of Cut off point

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Depression
Above-97.70	23	15.44 %	High
Between-97.70 to 66.18	100	67.11 %	Moderate
Below- 66.18	26	17.45 %	Low
Total	149	100%	

Figure: 1. Graphical representation of the level of Depression of the Unemployed Educated Person on basis of Cut off point

Table No-3: Results of t-Test between different groups of Unemployed Educated Person with regard to Their Depression.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference	S _{ED}	df	t-value	Result
Gender	Males	94	78.78	13.93	8.57	2.59	147	3.31**	S
	Females	55	87.35	17.29					
Residence	Rural	106	80.92	14.80	3.52	2.84	147	1.24@	NS
	Urban	43	84.44	17.84					
	Rural Males	77	78.36	12.72	9.36	3.11	104	3.01**	S
	Rural Females	29	87.72	17.78					
	Urban Males	17	80.65	18.83	6.23	5.55	41	1.13@	NS
	Urban Females	26	86.92	17.07					
	Rural Males	77	78.36	12.72	2.28	3.75	92	0.61@	NS
	Urban Males	17	80.65	18.83					
	Rural Females	29	87.72	17.78	0.80	4.71	53	0.17@	NS
	Urban Females	26	86.92	17.01					

*Significant at 0.05, ** Significant at 0.01 and @ Not Significant [Table Value of 't' against df-147, 104, 41, 92, 53 at 0.05 level and 0.01 level are 1.98, 2.02, 1.99, 2.01 & 2.61, 2.63, 2.71, 2.68 respectively]

Table No-4 : Shows the Number, Mean and S.D of Unemployed Educated Person of difference groups on the basis of Caste, Educational Qualification and Age with regard to Depression.

Different Aspects	Group/Variable	N	Mean	S.D
Caste	U.R	64	79.63	15.11
	OBC	42	82.50	13.75
	SC	40	84.98	18.03

	ST	03	83.00	24.56
Educational Qualification	H.S	26	68.46	10.22
	B.A/B.Sc/B.Com	26	86.77	13.62
	M.A/M.Sc/M.Com	28	86.21	18.23
	B.Ed/M.Ed	55	82.93	13.91
	M.Phil/Ph.D	14	85.57	17.52
Age Group	18-25	65	80.29	16.67
	26-35	71	82.62	14.77
	Above 35	13	86.46	16.36
Various State	Bihar	5	76.40	11.349
	Delhi	5	90.00	15.748
	Goa	3	86.00	10.817
	Gujarat	4	81.25	12.176
	Haryana	3	66.33	11.676
	Jharkhand	3	88.33	9.452
	Karnataka	4	74.25	14.175
	Kerala	6	78.50	16.538
	Maharashtra	6	75.83	12.671
	Manipur	3	87.00	9.165
	Odisha	3	76.00	18.083
	Uttar Pradesh	17	79.65	11.953
	Uttarakhand	4	81.50	9.147
	West Bengal	71	84.15	18.025
	Madhya Pradesh	3	84.33	6.807
Rajasthan	9	78.89	17.681	

Table No-5: Shows the results of ANOVA on different groups of Unemployed Educated Person with regard to Depression.

Different aspects of	Sum of Squares		Mean Square		F-value
	Between Groups	Within Groups	Between Groups	Within Groups	
Category	727.98	36014.48	242.660	248.38	0.98@
Educational Qualification	6079.53	30662.93	1519.88	212.94	7.14**
Age Group	475.05	36267.41	237.52	248.41	0.96@
Various State	2636.36	34106.10	175.76	256.44	0.69@

*Significant at 0.05, ** Significant at 0.01 and @ Not Significant [Table Value of 'F' against df-3/145, 4/144, 2/146, 15/133 at 0.05 and 0.01 level are 2.66, 2.43, 3.06, 1.83 and 3.91, 2.45, 4.75, 2.33 respectively]

Figure 2: Graphical Representation of the Depression of Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of Different Category.

Figure 3: Graphical Representation of the Depression of Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of Educational Qualification.

Figure 4: Graphical Representation of the Depression of Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of Age Groups.

Figure 5: Graphical Representation of the Depression of Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of Various States.

Testing of H_0 , and Interpretation:

On the basis of Cut off Point, from the [Table No-2](#), we can see that out of the total 149 Unemployed Educated Person, 15.44% Unemployed Educated Person have scored Above 97.70, 67.11% Unemployed Educated Person have scored Between 97.70 to 66.18 and 17.45% Unemployed Educated Person have scored

Below 66.18 on the Depression measuring Questionnaire constructed by the researchers for the Unemployed Educated Person. Therefore, it can be said that the maximum percentage (67.11%) of Unemployed Educated Person has scored Between 97.70 to 66.18, which indicates that the level of Depression of Unemployed Educated Person is being Moderate in India.

Testing of H_{0_2} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**3.31**) is greater than the table value at the 0.01 level of significance (2.61 at 0.01 level of significance). Therefore, the result is significant and it indicates that there is a significant difference between Male and Female Unemployed Educated persons with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Female Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than the Males Unemployed Educated Person in India.

Testing of H_{0_3} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**1.24**) is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance (1.98 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Unemployed Educated persons with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Urban Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Rural Unemployed Educated Person.

Testing of H_{0_4} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**3.01**) is greater than the table value at the 0.01 level of significance (2.63 at 0.01 level of significance). Therefore, the result is significant and it indicates that there is a significant difference between Rural Male and Rural Female Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that Rural Female Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Rural Male Unemployed Educated Person.

Testing of H_{0_5} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**1.13**) is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance (2.02 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Urban Male and Urban Female Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that Urban Female Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Urban Male Unemployed Educated Person.

Testing of H_{0_6} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**0.61**) is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance (1.99 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural Male and Urban Male Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that Urban Male Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Rural Male Unemployed Educated Person.

Testing of H_{0_7} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-3](#), it is observed that the calculated 't'-value (**0.80**) is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance (2.01 at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the result is not significant and it indicates that there is no significant difference between Rural Female and Urban Female Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. On the other hand, on the basis of the obtained Mean Scores, it can be said that the Rural Female Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Urban Female Unemployed Educated Person.

Testing of H_{0_8} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-5](#), it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is **0.98** which is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the result is not significant and we can say that there is no significant difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Caste. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Testing of H_{0_9} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-5](#), it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is **7.14** which is greater than the table value at the 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the result is significant and we can say that there is a significant difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Educational Qualification. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Testing of $H_{0_{10}}$ and Interpretation:

From [Table No-5](#), it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is 0.96 which is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the result is not significant and we can say that there is no significant

difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Age group. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Testing of H_{01} and Interpretation:

From [Table No-5](#), it is observed that the calculated 'F'-ratio is **0.69** which is less than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the result is not significant and we can say that there is no significant difference among the Unemployed Educated Person with respect to their level of Depression on the basis of Various States. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Major Findings and Discussion of the Results:

Through the present study found that there is a Moderate level of Depression among the Unemployed Educated Person in India ([Figure-1](#)). This finding of the study is supported by [Kim and Knesebeck \(2016\)](#); [Stirling et al. \(2015\)](#); [Karmakar and Behera \(2017\)](#); [Pachaiyappan and Siranjeevi \(2018\)](#). It is explored that the Depression of Females Unemployed Educated Person is higher than that of the Males Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of their obtained mean score. This finding of the present study is corroborated by [Afifi \(2006\)](#); [Ahmad and Mazlan \(2014\)](#); [Kapustinskiene et al. \(2006\)](#); [Chen, Wenjun \(2018\)](#); [Pachaiyappan and Siranjeevi \(2018\)](#); [Makelele and Wewirhu \(2017\)](#); [Anitha and chowdary \(2018\)](#). It is found that Urban Unemployed Educated Person was more depressed than Rural Unemployed Educated Persons and Rural Females Unemployed Educated Persons are more depressed than Rural Males Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Naik and Padikkal, 2016](#)). In this study explored that Urban Females Unemployed Educated Person are comparatively more depressed than Urban Males Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of their obtained mean score. This finding is supported by [Heubeck et al. \(1995\)](#). And also found that Urban Males Unemployed Educated Persons are more depressed than Rural Males Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Naik and Padikkal, 2016](#)) as well as the Rural Females Unemployed Educated Persons are comparatively more depressed than Urban Females Unemployed Educated Person on the basis of their obtained mean score.

This study revealed that Unemployed Educated Person who belongs to the unreserved category is comparatively low depressed than the other category and the Unemployed Educated Person who belongs to Schedule Caste Category is comparatively high depressed than another category on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Figure-2](#)). This finding is supported by [Karmakar and Behera \(2017\)](#). And also found that Unemployed Educated Person who passed Higher Secondary School is comparatively low depressed than other Educational Qualification persons and the Unemployed Educated Person who passed B.A/B.Sc/B.Com is comparatively high depressed than other Educational Qualification persons on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Figure-3](#)). This finding of the study is supported by [Yeh et al. \(2007\)](#); [Yousefi et al. \(2010\)](#); [Basnet et al. \(2012\)](#); [Arslan et al. \(2009\)](#); [Khurshid et al. \(2015\)](#). It is also found that Unemployed Educated Person who belongs to 18 to 25 Age group is comparatively low depressed than other Age groups and the Unemployed Educated Person who belongs to the Above 35 Age group is comparatively high depressed than other Age groups on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Figure-4](#)). This finding of the present study is followed by [Kapustinskiene et al. \(2006\)](#); [Yousefi et al. \(2010\)](#); [Dhara and Jogsan \(2013\)](#).

Lastly, This study found that the Unemployed Educated Person who lives in the state of Haryana is comparatively low depressed than the other States of India and the Unemployed Educated Persons who live in the State of Delhi is comparatively high depressed than the other State of India on the basis of their obtained mean score ([Figure-5](#)).

Conclusion

The present study found that there is a Moderate level of Depression among the Unemployed Educated Person. Urban Unemployed Educated Person was comparatively more depressed than Rural Unemployed Educated Person. Depression of Females and Unemployed Educated Person is comparatively higher than that of the Males Unemployed Educated Person. It is also found that Urban Males Unemployed Educated Persons are comparatively more depressed than Rural Males Unemployed Educated Person. Unemployed Educated Person who belongs to Schedule Caste Category is comparatively high depressed than other categories and Unemployed Educated Person who passed B.A/B.Sc/B.Com is comparatively high depressed than other Educational Qualification persons. It is also found that the Unemployed Educated Person who lives in the State of Delhi is comparatively high depressed than the other State of India.

However, that Depression is a type of mental disorder which in turn hinders the provision of compatibility with different environments and conditions. In depressed persons show the symptoms of low self-esteem, self-blame, hopelessness, suicide thoughts, anger, and peevishness ([Al-Qaisy, 2011](#)). Depression makes a person lonely from crowd society. Again the unemployed person is going to be the most noticed among them. As a result, many times they suffer from inferiority complex and worry about their future. It is hoped that this study will be particularly helpful to parents or guardians, counselors or guiders, administrators in providing guidance, counseling, and treatments to depressed individuals.

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